

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

1 Data

The data covers the period from January 1, 2019, to September 30, 2023, resulting in 41,593 time steps. It includes hourly information on patients' care categories, total care minutes, the total number of patients, as well as the number of admissions and discharges for one hospital ward from a German university hospital. In addition to the hospital data, we incorporated publicly available data on public holidays and school holidays in the region (STÜBER SYSTEMS GmbH, 2024). We also added calendar features and applied sine and cosine transformations to capture the cyclic nature of these calendar features. The dataset includes the period of COVID-19 lockdowns in Germany, during which hospital structures temporarily changed, resulting in a notable reduction in care minutes. To account for these irregularities, we included a Boolean feature indicating whether a COVID-19 lockdown was in effect. We identified the lockdown periods by visually inspecting the time series data and manually labelled the outliers.

The following table lists all features used for training our models.

Feature	Frequency	Range	Source
<i>Care demand in minutes</i>	Hourly, between 6 am and 10 pm	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
Number of patients in category $Ax/Sy, x, y = \{1,2,3,4\}$	Hourly, between 6 am and 10 pm	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
Care minutes for admittance per category $Ax/Sy, x, y = \{1,2,3,4\}$	Hourly, between 6 am and 10 pm	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
Care minutes for discharge per category $Ax/Sy, x, y = \{1,2,3,4\}$	Hourly, between 6 am and 10 pm	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
Care minutes per category $Ax/Sy, x, y = \{1,2,3,4\}$	Hourly, between 6 am and 10 pm	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
<i>Total number of patients</i>	Hourly	\mathbb{N}	University hospital
Covid flag	Daily	$\{0,1\}$	-
Public holiday	Daily	$\{0,1\}$	STÜBER SYSTEMS GmbH (2024)
School holiday	Daily	$\{0,1\}$	STÜBER SYSTEMS GmbH (2024)
Sine transformed day of week	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Cosine transformed day of week	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Sine transformed day of year	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Cosine transformed day of year	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Sine transformed day of month	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Cosine transformed day of month	Daily	$[-1,1]$	-
Sine transformed month of year	Monthly	$[-1,1]$	-
Cosine transformed month of year	Monthly	$[-1,1]$	-
Sine transformed hour of day	Hourly	$[-1,1]$	-
Cosine transformed hour of day	Hourly	$[-1,1]$	-

Table 1. List of features used for training the machine learning models, including their frequency, range, and source. The target values to be predicted by the models are highlighted in italics.

We trained two LightGBM models with different target time series. One was trained to predict the care demand in minutes, the other one was trained to predict the total number of patients. For further information on the two target time series, please refer to the paper.

Since care minutes are recorded only between 6 am and 10 pm in Germany, while patient numbers are available for every hour of the day, we trained the models on different data subsets for each scenario. For the care minute forecast, we utilized data from 6 am to 10 pm, resulting in 27,696 timesteps and a forecast horizon of 480 hours (30 days). For the total patient number forecast, we used the entire dataset with a horizon of 720 hours (30 days).

2 Training Details

For training, we utilised the implementations provided by Herzen et al. (2022). For LightGBM, we conducted a grid search with 30 trials to obtain the hyperparameters using the validation set. For TSMixer, hyperparameter tuning was performed using the framework by Liaw et al. (2018).

The following tables show the hyperparameter search spaces and the chosen hyperparameters per model.

2.1 LightGBM

Hyperparameter	Search space	Selected Values
Learning rate	{0.00001, ..., 0.1}	0.1
Lags	{{[-16], [-112, -16], [-224, -112, -16]}	[-112, -16]
Lags past covariates	{{[-16], [-112, -16], [-224, -112, -16]}	[-224, -112, -16]
Lags future covariates	{{[16], [16, 112], [16, 112, 224]}	[-224, -112, -16]
Nr. of leaves	{15, 20, ..., 45, 50}	15
Nr. of estimators	{50, 60, ..., 90, 100}	80
Minimum child samples	{10, 20, 30, 40}	20

Table 2. Hyperparameters for LightGBM trained to predict the care demand in minutes.

Hyperparameter	Search space	Selected Values
Learning rate	{0.00001, ..., 0.1}	0.1
Lags	{{[-24], [-168, -24], [-336, -168, -24]}	[-168, -24]
Lags past covariates	{{[-24], [-168, -24], [-336, -168, -24]}	[-336, -168, -24]
Lags future covariates	{{[24], [24, 168], [24, 168, 336]}	[-336, -168, -24]
Nr. of leaves	{15, 20, ..., 45, 50}	35
Nr. of estimators	{50, 60, ..., 90, 100}	50
Minimum child samples	{10, 20, 30, 40}	30

Table 3. Hyperparameters for LightGBM trained to predict the total number of patients.

2.2 TSMixer

Hyperparameter	Search space	Selected Values
Learning rate	{0.00001, ..., 0.1}	0.001
Look-back	{16, 64, 224, 480}	480
Dropout	{0.1, ..., 0.9}	0.2
Nr. of mixing layers	{1,2,3,4}	3

Hidden size of first feed-forward layer	{64, 128, 256, 512}	256
Hidden state size	{64, 128, 256, 512}	256
Nr. of epochs	-	30
Batch size	-	32
Early stopping patience	-	10

Table 4. Hyperparameters for TSMixer trained to predict the care demand in minutes.

Hyperparameter	Search space	Selected Values
Learning rate	{0.00001, ... ,0.1}	0.01
Look-back	{24, 96, 336, 720}	24
Dropout	{0.1, ..., 0.9}	0.1
Nr. of mixing layers	{1,2,3,4}	2
Hidden size of first feed-forward layer	{64, 128, 256, 512}	128
Hidden state size	{64, 128, 256, 512}	128
Nr. of epochs	-	30
Batch size	-	32
Early stopping patience	-	10

Table 5. Hyperparameters for TSMixer trained to predict the total number of patients.

3 Additional Results

Table 6 shows the mean of the estimation’s deviation from the actual number of required nurses for each month in the test set.

It can be observed that the heterogeneous approach constantly outperforms the homogeneous approach. Both versions generally overestimate the number of required nurses, except for the heterogeneous approach in August, where it underestimates the requirement by 0.19 (LightGBM) and 0.75 (TSMixer) nurses. When considering rounded values, the heterogeneous estimation using LightGBM provides accurate estimates in June and August. The homogeneous approach using LightGBM consistently overestimates the required number of nurses by one nurse more than the heterogeneous approach each month. Similarly, TSMixer yields better results when considering the heterogeneous approach. Comparing the rounded forecasts of the best model (heterogeneous LightGBM) to the baseline shows that including machine learning predictions into shift planning can outperform the current practice. All models consistently outperform the baseline. Summing up the improvements of the best model (heterogeneous LightGBM) compared to the baseline, yields to an improvement of 5 nurses over the four months, i.e. using the predictions as decision support would have saved 5 nurses when planning compared to when no decision support was available.

Predicted staffing needs		June	July	August	September
Heterogeneous	LightGBM	0.01 (0)	1.39 (1)	-0.19 (0)	0.81 (1)
	TSMixer	0.17 (0)	0.90 (1)	-0.75 (-1)	0.76 (1)
Homogeneous	LightGBM	0.85 (1)	1.77 (2)	0.77 (1)	1.49 (2)
	TSMixer	0.66 (1)	1.57 (2)	0.50 (1)	1.15 (1)
Baseline	Naive Seasonal	1.40 (1)	2.03 (2)	1.87 (2)	1.69 (2)

Table 6. Monthly average error of required nurses estimated from the heterogeneous and homogeneous approaches and the baseline. The rounded values are shown in brackets. The best models per month are highlighted in bold.

Figure 1: Actual and predicted required nurses in FTE from June 1, 2023, to June 30, 2023.

References

- Herzen, J., Lässig, F., Piazzetta, S. G., Neuer, T., Tafti, L., Raille, G., Van Pottelbergh, T., Pasieka, M., Skrodzki, A., Huguenin, N., & others. (2022). Darts: User-friendly modern machine learning for time series. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 23(124), 1–6.
- STÜBER SYSTEMS GmbH. (2024). *Open Holidays API*. Retrieved October 24, 2024 from <https://www.openholidaysapi.org/en/>
- R. Liaw, E. Liang, R. Nishihara, P. Moritz, J. E. Gonzalez, and I. Stoica (2018). Tune: A research platform for distributed model selection and training. arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.05118